

Designing an Optimal Safe Layout for a Fuel Storage Tanks Farm: Case Study of Jarpur Oil Depot

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Abstract : Storage tank farms are essential industrial facilities to accumulate oil, petrochemicals and gaseous products. Since tank farms contain huge mass of fuel and hazardous materials, they are always targets of serious accidents such as fire, explosion, spill and toxic release which may cause severe impacts on human health, environmental and properties. Although having a safe layout is not able to prevent initiating accidents, however it effectively controls and reduces the adverse impact of such accidents. The aim of this paper is to determine the optimal layout for a storage tank contains different type of hydrocarbon fuels. A quantitative risk assessment is carried out on a selected tank farm in Jaipur, India, with particular attention given to both the consequence modelling and the overall risk assessment using PHAST Software. Various designs of tank layouts are examined taking into consideration several issues of plant operations and maintenance. In all stages of the work, standard guidelines specified by the industry are considered and recommendations are substantiated with simulation results and risk quantification.

Keywords : tank farm, safe distance, safe layout, risk assessment, PHAST

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